

PEDAGOGICAL COOPERATION IN STUDENTS' INTEREST FORMATION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The current research paper discusses the development of interest and motivation of students in grades 6-7 to physical culture alongside with the main issues of forming a valuable attitude towards physical activities and a healthy lifestyle among students.*

Keywords: *physical culture, motivation, interest, teachers, students, gaming, methods, well-being and health promotion.*

Introduction. Central Asian countries, including Uzbekistan, were the center of science, culture and education. Historically, our ancestors, along with knowledge and intelligence, distinguished by strength, physical will and high military potential. One of the main reasons for this is that our ancestors have always been involved in national sports, wrestling, and physical exercise. The development of modern information technologies has aroused an increased interest among our youth in computer technology and mobile devices.

Main part. In our country and in the world, interest in the field of physical education and sports is increasing. Especially during the pandemic, it has become much clear that proper use of physical activity is effective in maintaining health. This led to the expansion of the sphere of physical education and sports, and the emergence of a need for cooperation between different spheres. From now on, the need to study problems in this area and its industry sectors are very important spheres to address in our days. Thus, the introduction of various areas in the field of physical education and sports, the desire to use physical education and sports in free time, the growing interest in sports competitions strengthen the process of increasing demand for innovative developments in this area.

In the process of physical education and sports training, people observe the use of various innovative sports equipment, the introduction of digital technologies in the organization of competitions, the formation of skills in using innovative changes in the development of their physical condition, and their use.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention paid to the further development of the physical education field and sports. The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-6099 dated October 30, 2020 "On measures for the widespread introduction of a healthy lifestyle and the further development of mass sports" notes "The emergence of the coronavirus pandemic COVID-19 in the world has shown a low level of physical health and a healthy lifestyle population of Uzbekistan, as in a number of other countries.

Under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat M. Mirziyoyev, on March 19, 2019, certain five important initiatives were aimed at increasing attention to youth, broadly introducing the younger generation to culture, art, physical culture and sports, as well as ensuring the quality of education.

Coronavirus pandemic COVID-19 has had a negative impact on the health of fellow citizens suffering primarily from cardiovascular diseases, respiratory diseases and obesity (overweight). As a result, today's pandemic has caused the premature death of many of our citizens.

The results of an analysis of the available scientific and methodological literature indicate that in recent years there has been an increase in the number of people with different levels of physical wealth who are prone to diseases.

The situation that has arisen today requires all of us to draw serious conclusions, get rid of bad habits, regularly engage in mass sports, follow the principles of proper nutrition, in particular, refrain from excessive consumption of foods high in salt, sugar and fat, as well as flour dishes, sweets and bread. Solving the defined tasks in the Presidential Decrees poses enormous challenges for industry specialists.

In the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 24, 2020 No. UP-5924 “On measures for further improvement and popularization of physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, No. UP-6099 dated October 30, 2020 “On measures for the widespread introduction of a healthy lifestyle and further development of mass sports”, Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 3, 2020 No. PP-4877 “On measures to improve the personnel training system and increase scientific potential in the field of physical culture and sports” defines the following tasks [2]:

- creating conditions for physical education and mass sports in every family, “mahallas”, districts (cities), preschool, general secondary, secondary special, vocational and higher educational institutions, as well as other organizations;
- holding sports competitions to develop mass sports between families, classes, work teams and regions on an ongoing basis;
- introduce into practice the “Minute of Sports” physical exercises between classes (during a big break) in general education, vocational and higher educational institutions, and breathing exercises 2 minutes before the start of classes;
- starting from the 2021/2022 academic year, develop criteria for assessing physical indicators (running, throwing, jumping, pulling up) of pupils and students depending on the age category, enter these indicators into a separate page of the “Kundalik” rating book, ensuring that the relevant analyzes and results are displayed in the context every quarter;
- conducting fundamental research in the field of physical culture and sports; educational standards and scientific programs, textbooks and teaching aids, including audio, video and electronic textbooks in the field of physical education and sports for all types of education in the country, online lesson preparation, etc.

Conclusion. The above regulatory documents emphasize the importance of mass sports in the life of an individual and family in all regions of our country, the importance and relevance of the tasks of promoting the fact that it is the basis of physical and spiritual health, of protecting young people from bad habits, of creating the necessary conditions for them to realize their abilities and talents, select talented athletes from them, and improve the target training system.

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